

3,4-Coumarin-Pyrones: Part III—Pechmann Condensation of 4-Hydroxycoumarin with Ethyl Acetonedicarboxylate

Jimmy Patell and R. N. Usgaonkar

4-Hydroxycoumarin condensed smoothly with ethyl acetonedicarboxylate in presence of anhydrous $AlCl_3$, furnishing a mixture of coumarino(3', 4', 5, 6)-4-carboethoxymethyl- α -pyrone, -4-carboxymethyl- α -pyrone and -4-methyl- α -pyrone. Condensation of 4-hydroxy-6-methylcoumarin and 4-hydroxy-8-methylcoumarin furnished similar mixtures.

Pechmann Condensation of a number of 4-hydroxycoumarins with ethyl acetoacetate and ethyl α -methylacetoacetate has been reported earlier.¹ The present paper deals with the condensation of 4-hydroxycoumarins with ethyl acetonedicarboxylate.

4-Hydroxycoumarin (Ia) condensed smoothly with ethyl acetone-dicarboxylate when anhydrous $AlCl_3$ was used as condensing agent and nitrobenzene as solvent. The reaction, however, gave a mixture of three products: (A) coumarino(3', 4', 5, 6)-4-carboethoxymethyl- α -pyrone (IIa, $Y=CH_2COOEt$), (B) coumarino(3', 4', 5, 6)-4-carboxymethyl- α -pyrone (IIa, $Y=CH_2COOH$) and (C) coumarino(3', 4', 5, 6)-4-methyl- α -pyrone (IIa, $Y=Me$). The condensation can normally be expected to give the product A. The formation of other products B and C must have resulted by the hydrolysis of the ester group in A and subsequent decarboxylation in the presence of strong Lewis acid $AlCl_3$.

(I)

(II)

a : $R_1 = H$; $R_2 = H$

b : $R_1 = H$; $R_2 = Me$

c : $R_1 = Me$; $R_2 = H$.

The component C of the mixture was identified by taking mixed m.p. with an authentic specimen (IIa, $Y=Me$) synthesised earlier.^{1,2} The component B on decarboxylation furnished the component C and on esterification with ethanol furnished A. The component A on hydrolysis with alkali or acid furnished B. These reactions thus established the structures (IIa, $Y=CH_2COOEt$) and (IIa, $Y=CH_2COOH$) assigned to A and B respectively.

1. Patell and Usgaonkar, (a) *Curr. Sci.*, 1963, 32, 406; (b) *this Journal*, 1965, 42: 215; (c) *this Journal*, *in press*.

Condensation of 4-hydroxy-6-methylcoumarin (Ib) and of 4-hydroxy-8-methylcoumarin(Ic) with ethyl acetonedicarboxylate in presence of anhydrous $AlCl_3$ furnished similar mixtures. The condensation of the former gave a mixture of A) (IIb, $Y=CH_2COOEt$), (B) (IIb, $Y=CH_2COOH$) and (C) (IIb, $Y=Me$). The condensation of the latter gave a mixture of (A) (IIc, $Y=CH_2COOEt$), (B) (IIc, $Y=CH_2COOH$) and (C) (IIc, $Y=Me$). The components C of these mixtures were identified by taking mixed m.p. with the authentic specimens synthesised earlier^{1a,b}. The structures of the other components were established by interconversion as before.

It was observed that better yields of the products were obtained when excess of ethyl acetonedicarboxylate was used in the condensations. The coumarin, the ester and $AlCl_3$ in the molar proportion of 1:3:2 were used in all the condensations. Attempts to effect the condensations using concentrated sulphuric acid as condensing agent did not succeed.

EXPERIMENTAL

Condensation of 4-Hydroxycoumarin(Ia) with Ethyl Acetonedicarboxylate.—4-Hydroxycoumarin^a (2.5 g.) and ethyl acetonedicarboxylate (10 g.) were added to a solution of anhydrous $AlCl_3$ (4 g.) in dry $PhNO_2$ (20 ml.) and the mixture was heated in an oilbath at 110° for 4 hr. Crushed ice and conc. HCl were added to the mixture and $PhNO_2$ was removed by steam distillation. The crude solid (yield 2.5 g) that was left behind, was triturated with aq. $NaHCO_3$ and filtered. The *insoluble residue A* (1.7 g.) was thus separated from *soluble portion B* (0.5 g.) which was recovered by acidification of the filtrate.

Insoluble residue A: This was refluxed with ethanol (50 ml.) and filtered. The residue had m.p. $245-46^\circ$ and crystallised from benzene in silky needles. It was identified as coumarino(3', 4', 5, 6)-4-methyl- α -pyrone.^{1a,b} (IIa, $Y=Me$) by mixed m.p. determination. The ethanolic solution (filtrate) was concentrated to a small bulk and allowed to cool when a substance with m.p. $195-215^\circ$ crystallised out. This was heated with dil. aq. NaOH (5 ml.; 10%) on steam bath for 15 min. The resulting solution was acidified with HCl and the precipitated solid was triturated with aq. $NaHCO_3$ and filtered. The residue was identified as (IIa, $Y=Me$), m.p. and mixed m.p. with an authentic specimen, $245-46^\circ$. The filtrate on acidification with HCl gave coumarino(3', 4', 5, 6)-4-carboxymethyl- α -pyrone (IIa, $Y=CH_2COOH$). It crystallised from ethanol in plates, m.p. $245-46^\circ$ (decomp.). (Found: C, 62.0; H, 3.3. $C_{14}H_8O_6$ requires C, 61.8; H, 3.0%.) This acid was then esterified by refluxing with ethanol (25 ml.) and conc. H_2SO_4 (1 ml.) for 18-20 hr., for regenerating the original ester. On cooling the solution, coumarino(3', 4', 5, 6)-4-carboethoxymethyl- α -pyrone (IIa, $Y=CH_2COOEt$) crystallised out. After washing it thoroughly with aq. $NaHCO_3$ and water, it was crystallised from ethanol in needles, m.p. $154-56^\circ$. (Found: C, 64.4; H, 4.4. $C_{16}H_{12}O_6$ requires C, 64.0; H, 4.0%.)

Soluble portion B: This crystallised from ethanol in plates with no sharp m.p.; yield, 0.32 g. On concentrating the mother liquor unchanged 4-hydroxycoumarin (small amount) crystallised out, m.p. and mixed m.p. with an authentic specimen $210-11^\circ$. The substance with no sharp m.p. was subjected to esterification with ethanol (30 ml.) ad conc. H_2SO_4 (1 ml.) as before. On cooling the solution, the ester (IIa, $Y=CH_2COOEt$) crystallised out.

After washing the crystals with aq. NaHCO_3 (by trituration) and water to remove unchanged Ia, it was recrystallised from ethanol in needles m.p. and mixed m.p. with the previous specimen (from residue A), 154-50°. This ester, on hydrolysis with dil. aq. NaOH as before or by refluxing with HCl (1.1) furnished the acid (IIa, $\text{Y}=\text{CH}_2\text{COOH}$). It crystallised in plates, m.p. and mixed m.p. with the previous specimen 245-46° (decomp.).

M.p.s of (IIa, $\text{Y}=\text{CH}_2\text{COOH}$) and of (IIa, $\text{Y}=\text{Me}$) are same and their mixed m.p. shows no depression. Former is soluble in aq. NaHCO_3 while the latter is insoluble. It appears that the former gets decarboxylated completely to give the latter near about the m.p. of the latter.

Decarboxylation of (IIa, $\text{Y}=\text{CH}_2\text{COOH}$) (0.1 g) was carried out by heating it in metal bath at about 270° for about half an hour. The product was insoluble in aq. NaHCO_3 and crystallised from benzene in needles, m.p. and mixed m.p. with the authentic specimen of (IIa, $\text{Y}=\text{Me}$) 245-46°.

Condensation of 4-Hydroxy-6-methylcoumarin (Ib) with Ethyl Acetonedicarboxylate.—The coumarin Ib^a (3.5 g.) and ethyl acetonedicarboxylate (12 g.) and anhydrous AlCl_3 (5.4 g.) in dry PhNO_2 (24 ml.) were mixed together and heated at 110° for 4 hr. and then worked up in the usual manner. The crude product (yield 5.1 g.) was triturated with aq. NaHCO_3 and filtered. The *insoluble residue A* (4.2 g.) was thus separated from *soluble portion B* (0.6 g) which was recovered by acidification of the filtrate.

Insoluble residue A. It had m.p. 135-45°. On crystallisation from ethanol (50 ml.) a substance with m.p. 150-60° (1.5 g.) separated as clusters of needles. The mother liquor was concentrated and cooled when coumarino (3', 4', 5, 6)-4, 6'-dimethyl- α -pyrone (IIb, $\text{Y}=\text{Me}$) crystallised out. It was recrystallised from benzene in needles, m.p. and mixed m.p. with an authentic specimen^{1a,b}, 197-98°. The substance with m.p. 150-60° was heated with dil aq. NaOH (30 ml.; 10%) on boiling waterbath for 15 min. The resulting solution, on acidification with HCl gave a solid. This was triturated with aq. NaHCO_3 and filtered. The residue was identified as (IIb, $\text{Y}=\text{Me}$), m.p. and mixed m.p. with an authentic specimen^{1a,b} 197-98°. The filtrate, on acidification with HCl gave coumarino (3', 4', 5, 6)-4-carboxymethyl-6'-methyl- α -pyrone (IIb, $\text{Y}=\text{CH}_2\text{COOH}$). It crystallised from ethanol in needles, m.p. 201-02°. (Found: C, 63.1; H, 3.9. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_6$ requires C, 62.9; H, 3.5%). This acid was then esterified by refluxing with ethanol (30 ml.) and conc. H_2SO_4 (1 ml.) for 18-20 hr. On cooling the solution, coumarino (3', 4', 5, 6)-4-carboethoxymethyl-6'-methyl- α -pyrone (IIb, $\text{Y}=\text{CH}_2\text{COOEt}$) crystallised out. After washing it with aq. NaOH (by trituration) and water, it was crystallised from ethanol in needles m.p. 191-92°. (Found: C, 64.9; H, 4.8. $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{14}\text{O}_6$ requires C, 65.0; H, 4.5).

The soluble portion B. This was crystallised from ethanol when a substance with m.p. 190-98° was obtained (yield, 0.2 g.). On concentrating the mother liquor, unchanged (Ib) crystallised out, m.p. and mixed m.p. with an authentic specimen 253-54°. The substance with m.p. 190-98° was subjected to esterification by refluxing ethanol (25 ml.) and conc. H_2SO_4 (1 ml.) for 18 hr. The ester (IIb, $\text{Y}=\text{CH}_2\text{COOEt}$) crystallised out on cooling the solution. After washing these crystals with aq. NaHCO_3 to remove unchanged Ib, they were recrystallised from ethanol in needles, m.p. and mixed m.p. with the previous specimen (from residue A) 191-92°. This ester, on hydrolysis with dil aq. NaOH in the usual manner, furnished the original acid (IIb, $\text{Y}=\text{CH}_2\text{COOH}$), m.p. and mixed m.p. with the previous specimen, 201-02°.

Decarboxylation of (IIb, $Y=CH_3COOH$) (0.1 g.) was carried out by heating it in a metal bath at 250° for about 1/2 hr. The product was insoluble in aq. $NaHCO_3$ and crystallised from benzene (charcoal) in needles, m.p. and mixed m.p. with an authentic specimen of (IIb, $Y=Me$) 197-98°.

Condensation of 4-Hydroxy-8-methylcoumarin (Ic) with Ethyl Acetone dicarboxylate.—A mixture of Ic^a (3.5 g), ethyl acetonedicarboxylate (12.0 g.) and anhydrous $AlCl_3$ (5.4 g.) in dry $PhNO_2$ (24 ml.) was heated as usual, at 110° for 4 hr. The reaction was worked up as before and the crude product (4.2 g.) was triturated with aq. $NaHCO_3$ and filtered. The insoluble residue was thus separated from soluble portion B which was recovered by acidification of the filtrate.

Insoluble residue A (yield, 3.2 g.).—This was refluxed with ethanol (50 ml.) and filtered hot. The residue (m.p. 197-98°) crystallised from benzene in thin plates, m.p. 202-03°. It was identified as coumarino (3', 4', 5, 6)-4,8'-dimethyl- α -pyrone^{1a,b} (IIc, $Y=Me$) by taking mixed m.p. with the authentic specimen which remained undepressed. The filtrate (ethanolic solution) was concentrated to a small bulk and cooled when a substance, m.p. 150-80° crystallised out; yield, 1.2 g. This was heated with dil aq. $NaOH$ (25 ml.; 10%) for 15 min. on steam bath. The resulting solution was acidified with HCl and the precipitated solid was triturated with aq. $NaHCO_3$ and filtered. The residue was identified as (IIc, $Y=Me$), m.p. and mixed m.p. with an authentic specimen, 202-03°. The filtrate on acidification gave coumarino (3', 4', 5, 6)-4-carboxymethyl-8'-methyl- α -pyrone (IIc, $Y=CH_3COOH$). It crystallised from ethanol in plates m.p. 200-01°. (Found: C, 62.7; H, 3.4. $C_{17}H_{16}O_6$ requires C, 62.0; H, 3.5). The acid was then esterified by refluxing ethanol (30 ml.) and conc. H_2SO_4 (1 ml.) for 18 hr. The ester, coumarino(3', 4', 5, 6)-4-carboethoxymethyl-8'-methyl- α -pyrone (IIc, $Y=CH_3COOEt$) crystallised out on cooling the mixture. After washing it with aq. $NaHCO_3$ it was recrystallised from ethanol in needles, m.p. 174-75°. (Found: C, 65.0; H, 4.4. $C_{17}H_{18}O_6$ requires C, 65.0; H, 4.5%.)

The soluble portion B.—This crystallised from ethanol (50 ml.), m.p. 195-98°. On concentrating the mother liquor unchanged (Ic) was obtained. It crystallised from acetic acid in plates m.p. and mixed m.p. with the authentic specimen 227-28° (d). The substance with m.p. 195-98° was repeatedly crystallised from ethanol when it gave sharp m.p. 200-01°. It was identified as (IIc, $Y=CH_3COOH$) by taking mixed m.p. With the previous specimen (from residue A) which remained undepressed. This acid was esterified in the usual manner with ethanol and H_2SO_4 when the ester (IIc, $Y=CH_3COOEt$) was obtained. It crystallised from ethanol in needles, m.p. and mixed m.p. with the previous specimen (from residue A) 174-75°.

Decarboxylation of (IIc, $Y=CH_3COOH$) was carried out by heating it in a metal bath at 250° for about 1/2 hr. The product was insoluble in aq. $NaHCO_3$ and it crystallised from benzene in thin plates, m.p. and mixed m.p. with the authentic specimen of coumarino (3', 4', 5, 6)-4,8'-dimethyl- α -pyrone^{1a,b} 202-03°.

The authors offer their thanks to Shri R. S. Kulkarni for microanalyses of the samples.